

Digital Marketing Strategy

Research infographic

Marketing Campaign: "Bollyqueer: Empowering Through Dance"

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Marketing Campaign: "Bollyqueer: Empowering Through Dance"

Justification

Given that Bollyqueer's strategic approach of digital and content marketing together with targeted audience interaction dovetail with the rising demand for more culturally diverse and inclusive performances, the potential of this business is apparent. Thus, in addition to targeting a specific

yet previously unrepresented market segment, Bollyqueer utilizes successful cultural events and powerful self-stories of people in the community to raise awareness and promote social acceptance.

Bollyqueer Marketing Campaign Strategy Using the SOSTAC Framework

The SOSTAC framework is a comprehensive model for developing marketing and business strategies, encompassing six phases: Situation Analysis, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics and Action. This structured approach ensures that strategies are well-founded, efficiently executed, and effectively managed (Chaffey and Chadwick, 2019).

Figure: SOSTAC Framework (Sawicki, 2020)

Situation Analysis

Internal Analysis

Bollyqueer is a new class specially designed for the queer community wherein people will learn Bollywood dance. It encourages self-empowerment since it combats the stereotypical gender roles while providing an environment that affirms the participants' identities during the performance of dance (Bollyqueer, 2023). The classes are very inclusive and open to all gender identities and to express yourself in a very open and accepting environment.

External Analysis

The competition is stiff due to other groups that include, Alpha Dancers and Rainbow Nation, are the other groups that perform dances that are relevant to the theme. However, there already exist groups that perform for and organize events for the LGBTQ+ community, and while some of them are involved in Bollywood dance, Bollyqueer occupies a unique niche in this landscape (Gibrona, 2023).

SWOT Analysis

- **Strengths:** Bollyqueer has major advantages due to its addressing of the niche topic of queer Bollywood dance exclusively. This approach makes it unique in the dancing fraternity as it offers specialty in certain areas. Also, Bollyqueer experiences much support from the members of the community, and people eliminate prejudice.
- **Weaknesses:** However, there are several shortcomings that Bollyqueer has; it has a small coverage area, and the number of classes it teaches is meager currently. The need to access a large number of consumers and expand the number of classes (Ryan, 2023).
- **Opportunities:** The lack of mainstream queer POC events shows that there is more potential for Bollyqueer to fully realize its mission and grow its product line. Another source of great opportunity is potential corporation affiliation.
- **Threats:** This is because there are other dance groups that are specifically formed to dance for the LGBTQ+ community, and thus they could pose a threat to Bollyqueer even with their slight focus difference (Rodriguez, 2021). Furthermore, there is a possibility that the general trends in a specific market and shifts in people's preferences will affect the viability and continued expansion of the classes.

Objectives

1. **Increase Bookings:** Attracting corporate clients, festivals, and events such as queer weddings for workshops and performances.
2. **Boost Class Sales:** Expanding the audience to generate higher demand for classes and increase the number of sessions offered.
3. **Enhance Publicity:** Developing a strategy to share press and news features, integrating personal stories.

Strategy

Target Audience

- **Businesses:** The primary type of client Bollyqueer identifies with encompasses enterprises and entities involved in hiring performances or workshops as part of major events like the South Asian Heritage Month and Pride Month (Gibrona, 2023). These businesses are seeking to introduce new and exciting initiatives at their events for employees, which would help break the traditional mold and embrace the proactive and progressive values of the company.
- **LGBTQ+ Community:** This site is designed for queer people who want to dance Bollywood with positive emotions and in a friendly environment. The classes are intended for those who want to study dancing while adopting the sexuality they feel comfortable with, without conforming to such stereotypical roles as a masculine or a feminine one.

Positioning

Bollyqueer is ascribed to be an affirmative Bollywood dancing lessons that sets focus on the LGBTQ+ populace in a manner that is quite uncommon. It is imperative to focus on the concept of the center as a place that would be comfortable for anyone regardless of the gender or preferences (Sabala, 2020). Therefore, through the disruption of gender and sexuality norms in Bollyqueer dance, the innovative form of Bollywood dance is shown through radical, freeing and liberating feels.

Unique Selling Proposition (USP)

Bollywood dance classes for sexually marginalized persons, Bollyqueer as a dance group is the only one in the dance industry that understands the need for queer persons. The unique selling proposition would be that Bollyqueer been committed to making a space where queer persons would practice Bollywood dance and not have to conform to certain gender norms (Szalacha, 2018). This dedication to equity and celebration sets Bollyqueer apart as an organization that has taken steps to make meaningful change in bringing more joyful dance opportunities to the LGBTQ+ community.

Tactics

Digital Marketing:

- **Social Media Campaigns:** Social media marketing is critical because it allows targeting a wide audience and frequent engagement with it. Promoting them in various social media platforms including Instagram, Facebook and twitter through sharing interesting and appealing stories, special features, and frequent class announcements (Chaffey and Chadwick, 2019). This means that through providing good content, a user or a brand can establish itself and be well received.
- **Influencer Partnerships:** Marketing strategies involving influencer collaborations are one of the most effective ways for increasing brand recognition and satisfaction. Engage prominent LGBTQ+ advocates to popularize bollyqueer courses as well as events (Sabala, 2020). They can post about the experiences they themselves had and draw attention towards the aspects of our dance classes that suit them.

Content Marketing:

- **Blog Posts and Articles:** This can be done by regularly releasing articles, videos, and blog posts to the Bollyqueer website and other popular LGBTQ+ media outlets. Some examples of topics to be covered include: The Importance of Dance, Integration, and Testimonials from Dancers (Ryan, 2023). Besides, these articles will help Bollyqueer to rank higher and become a valued voice in the sphere of dance and LGBTQ+ issues.

Action

- **Campaign Planning:** To achieve such a scenario, the following should be done: Timeline and responsibility for each tactic should be developed.
- **Content Creation:** The first task is to create content for social media platforms, blogs, and press releases.
- **Outreach:** First of all, it can help in starting communication with potential corporate customers, affecting their decision-making, and media outlets.
- **Event Coordination:** Organizing and participating in relevant events and festivals, and in particular.

Control

Metrics and KPIs:

- Measuring the web traffic, followers, and participants of the classes on the website and social media platforms.
- Tracking the number of companies and events that partner with the organization and the number of events that are being booked.

Feedback and Adjustments:

- Gathering responses from participants and partners in order to determine their views on the improvement of the program.
- Refinement of the strategy based on the performance information that was collected and received in the course of the implementation process in order to achieve the set goals and objectives.

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